

A CREATIVE APPROACH TO TEACHING IN PRIMARY GRADES

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Abstract. This article describes the creative teaching approach to elementary school classes.

Keywords: creativity, ability, integration, syncretism, problem situations.

ТВОРЧЕСКИЙ ПОДХОД К ОБУЧЕНИЮ В НАЧАЛЬНЫХ КЛАССАХ

Аннотация. В данной статье описывается творческий подход к обучению на уроках начальной школы.

Ключевые слова: креативность, способность, интеграция, синкретизм, проблемные ситуации.

INTRODUCTION

Creativity (lat., ing. "create" describing the readiness of the individual to produce new ideas and creativity, which is part of talent as an independent factor means ability. A person's creativity is in his thinking, it is manifested in communication, feelings, certain types of activities.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Creativity is a person as a whole or his specific features, mind describes sharpness. Also, creativity is an important factor of talent[1] therefore, first of all, teachers have the qualities of creativity to lead the lesson processes in a creative way, to encourage students to think out of the ordinary it is possible to effectively organize a lesson by teaching teachers can integrate creativity into all subjects. For example, mathematics creativity in science or unusual lessons such as creativity in science classes if organized, it can increase students' enthusiasm and interest in the lesson. Come now Let's say that we want to start an unusual lesson and start our lesson with the method of the mind wheel, and we ask the students a question: which professions wear two watches? Students are divided into 5 or 6 teams and given 1 minute to think, and after the end of the time, the team member is required to give his answer and prove it. Through this, it is possible to improve students' thinking, speed, speaking ability and unusual answers. This is certainly an example of the beginning of a creative lesson. In creative teaching, the teacher can use various cases, problem situations, practical assignments, and independent work assignments. In addition, we can form creative thinking skills through various roundtable discussions, debates, solutions and proposals. In addition, it is worth emphasizing the use of interactive methods in the effective organization of the lesson. For example:

1. Venn diagram
2. Fish skeleton
3. Case study
4. Singapore method
5. Zinven method
6. Insert
7. Cluster
8. Relationship method and rules.

RESULTS

Sinkwain is summarizing information is complicated express ideas, sensations, imaginations in a few words is an important skill in terms of ability to do. These are rich insights requires thoughtful reflection based on its reserve. This is Cinquain is a poem, which is written in connection with an event or of information and materials in reflective short expressions requires synthesis. Cinquain is a French word that means five. So, Cinquevain is a poem of five lines. The rule for writing a syncway is as follows:

1. In the first line, the subject is written with a comma (usually a noun with the word about).
2. In the second line, the topic is described with two words (to the adjective group with two words about).
3. In the third line, the actions on this topic are three words is characterized by
4. The fourth line consists of 4 words indicating relevance to the topic a sentence (phrase) is written.

Also, it is possible to conduct creative test tests from students through unfinished pictures of Torrance's various creativity tests. In the lessons, the teacher moves in the following four directions according to the "creativity road map" and the actions in them are considered signs of creativity of pedagogues:

- 1) demonstration of creative thinking skills;
- 2) to be able to use strategies (methods and tools) that encourage students to master academic subject with interest;
- 3) innovative approach and creative approach to finding solutions to pedagogical issues (problems);
- 4) the expected result.

DISCUSSION

In order for the teacher to have the potential of creativity, it is necessary to pay attention to the following in his professional activities: In order for the teacher to have the potential of creativity, it is necessary to pay attention to the following in his professional activities:

- speed and flexibility of thinking;
- the ability to create new ideas;
- not thinking in one way;
- originality;
- initiative; tolerance of uncertainty;
- to be intelligent.

CONCLUSIONS

Self-development and self-expression of each pedagogue is directly related to his creativity.[3] According to Ken Robinson, "creativity is a set of original ideas with their own value" (Azzam, 2009) is counted. And Gardner explains the concept in his research: "Creativity is a practical action carried out by a person, which reflect a certain novelty and have a certain practical value must". Expressed in terms of Emebayl's (1989) approach, creativity is "combined with thorough knowledge of a specific field to have unusual skills at a high level" means. At this point, it is worth noting that each person is different by nature has the ability to be creative. Well, teachers are creative in themselves How can they demonstrate their ability? In this place Patti Drapeau advises: "Don't pretend you're not creative if you think so, to develop creative thinking

right now I advise you to start organizing focused classes. Actually, it's not about whether or not you are creative and creative organize lessons in the spirit of creativity and put new ideas into practice is in your desire to try"2.[4]

REFERENCES

1. Instructional manual for the module "Basics of creative pedagogy" Tashkent-2016 [4] p.
2. Pedagogical technologies and pedagogical skills Tashkent-2006 N.N. Azizkho'jayeva
3. Fayllar.org - the pedagogical basis of forming the student's creativity.html
4. Teaching methodology manual for the module "Basics of creative pedagogy" Tashkent-2016 [20-21] page